

TECHNOLOGICAL SAFETY IN STUDENTS BASED ON AN INNOVATIVE APPROACH INTEGRATION OF THE SCIENCES OF SUPPLY

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Annotation. The content of the didactic principles of the integration of subjects to ensure the technological safety of students based on an innovative approach is logically, consistently, and scientifically described in the article.

Keywords. student, innovation, approach, integration, universal, disaster, problem, situation, nature, society, opportunity, competence, activity, factor, method, situation, active, attitude.

It is known that the last 20th century was the century of scientific and technical achievements. In addition to the use of scientific and technical progress, the current unfavorable environmental situation poses significant environmental risks.

It creates an environmental hazard of universal importance.

The causes of environmental risk Coordination of relations between nature, society, people and technology and prevention of environmental risk has become the main problem of today.

This unfavorable environmental situation has a significant impact on people. In this regard, universal and regional ecological danger, its causes, coordination of relations between man and nature, society and nature, prevention of environmental destruction are the urgent problems of today.

Materials studied in environmental education for schoolchildren are important in the process of getting to know nature directly. Nature is composed of the material world that surrounds man in its various forms. The goal of environmental education-education to schoolchildren is to teach them to know nature and to protect it, to form interdisciplinary theoretical knowledge, practical skills and competencies related to environmental education-education. The analysis shows the interdisciplinary formation of concepts of environmental education among schoolchildren.

Factors that help active mental activity in the process of integration of educational subjects during the inspection are the selection of methods, taking into account the appropriate combination of subjects for integration, the actions of the teacher and the student.

There are certain opportunities for integration of all subjects taught in general education schools, and its integrated organization depends on a number of conditions. That's why

pedagogues and methodologists should consider all these situations before creating a new program. One of the reasons for the difficulties in educational activities is not to use integration.

The reason for a student's successful mastery of one subject may also be related to the fact that they have good knowledge of another subject.

For example, in order to copy a large text literately, it is necessary to be able to read it quickly and correctly. Without talking about such a possibility, it is necessary to feel that

teaching every subject taught by the teacher without comparing it with another, without using its authorities, can be very difficult and harmful. Including discussion with students by organizing integrated classes, organizing interclass competitions, question-and-answer sessions. The main purpose of using such modern types of lessons is to activate students in the learning process, to achieve a high level of mastering the learning material. Such technology teaches the student to imagine the world in a different way, to connect practice with life, not to memorize theoretical rules verbatim.

The principle of interdisciplinarity ensures the full mastery of the complex aspects of interdisciplinary relations, providing access to the inner essence of knowledge. As a result, different systems are interrelated, integrative whole. In particular, connection between humanitarian sciences, ensuring mutual dependence, providing students with biological knowledge in accordance with a certain classification are prominent as a factor of forming their interest in learning about nature.

The use of ecological concepts in the course of the lesson creates interest in learning about ecology among high school students. In addition, in their education, the implementation of interdisciplinary connections, the understanding of the essence of the existence of nature and society, the events and processes that take place in them, the holistic visualization of general and specific concepts in the content of these academic subjects, the process of forming environmental concepts in the student through the formation of skills, skills and competencies in practice is important in creating.

Teaching ecology to students of general education The concepts that form the basis for the establishment of interdisciplinary communication in schools are divided into the following groups:

1. Continuity and integrity of the totality of events that occur on the basis of the interdependence of nature and society.
2. Implementation of interdisciplinarity through the use of the laws of nature and society in understanding life processes and changes, solving problematic educational tasks.
3. The need to study events and incidents in material existence, the causes of environmental disasters and measures to eliminate them.
4. Ways to learn the laws of nature and society and use them effectively and rationally.

Interdisciplinarity develops the student's ability to think, increases independence. Also, along with the development of his interest in science, he forms his work, skills and competences and greatly helps to educate his ecological culture.

Being in direct, active communication with nature and society accelerates the process of mental activity organized by students of general education schools. This situation affects the way of thinking of students, creates interest in learning about nature and improves their mental abilities.

Also, since today the issue of developing a humane attitude towards nature among students is a cross-sectional issue, during their work, pedagogues provide students with knowledge about the laws of nature and society, man and nature, their mutual balance, and the preservation of natural balance, and on the basis of these, educational and educational work on environmental topics. will have to plan and implement.

In particular, in the conditions of current environmental problems, ensuring environmental safety, leaving natural resources to the next generation, their rational use and protection, improving the legislation for this purpose, and strengthening environmental and

legal education and upbringing in the family remain a priority task. This will serve to preserve, respect, and rationally use and protect the existing natural resources of our country for future generations.

Ensuring communication in the educational process consists of the following:

- difference between animate and inanimate nature;
- artistic features of natural objects;
- ecological components of nature and their interrelation;
- natural phenomena and their artistic effect;
- Uzbekistan's nature and its ecological protection;
- forming a rational relationship to the nature around us.

It is desirable to bring students preliminary, ecological concepts based on the integration of sciences in the acquisition of ecological knowledge about the laws of nature and society's development. General education provides an opportunity for the formation of ecological concepts based on the integration of subjects in high school students.

Analyzing the program of natural sciences in accordance with the content, determining their continuous and organic connection of interdisciplinary environmental education, applying them in the educational process, and activating the student's cognitive activity are of great importance. Their integration in the teaching of natural sciences, that is, the implementation of horizontal-vertical connection between disciplines, is an important didactic condition of the educational process, which fulfills the following tasks:

1. The scientificity and density of the educational material, which is the main source of knowledge for students, ensures the didactic connection of concepts learned from other natural sciences.
2. The student's interest in acquiring knowledge increases and intellectual development accelerates.
3. Integrating natural sciences, that is, by implementing interdisciplinary horizontal and vertical stages in teaching, makes it possible to expand the scientific worldview of students.
4. Aspects of interaction between natural sciences and specific laws within the sciences are not limited to the expression of different knowledge and concepts in the content of specific academic subjects. Pedagogical research related to ensuring interdisciplinary connection in teaching should be considered as an independent research direction as an opportunity to exert pedagogical influence on the developing individual.

Sophisticated worldviews, scientific and ecological ideas are reflected in figurative topics that are easy for the reader to understand, and they allow to compile the contents of the year. The system in which these are regulated is a characteristic feature of integrative education.

The methods, forms and tools used in the educational process are different. As a result of the educational reforms implemented in our country, issues of harmonizing relations between society and the environment, establishing and developing a positive attitude towards the environment are of great importance in new curricula and during the transition to programs.

The teacher's creativity lies in the fact that they design aspects that are known to the subject, but the student does not know. If this is the case, it is an effective way to implement integration through the organization of module lessons to increase students' ecological thinking.

Based on the above points, considering the development of the student's ecological thinking in the teaching of natural sciences by connecting them horizontally and vertically, analyzing

the inter-curriculum and programs of natural sciences in secondary schools, determining the continuity between them, i.e. the inter-discipline connection, taking into account the age and psychological characteristics of students, the horizontal nature of natural sciences and there was a need to develop lesson plans for teaching in vertical connection and to create methodical recommendations for biology teachers.

In relation to natural sciences, several methods of integration are currently used.

The first is to combine into one discipline. The results of the study of international pedagogic experiences published in this issue are comprehensive, integrated courses are being created, a characteristic feature of many schools of foreign countries.

In improving ecological education, it is necessary to pay attention to the issues of environment, nature, human protection, correct and rational use of natural resources, cleanliness. These issues should be included in the curriculum, educational programs, optional training, and work plans.

The use of biochemical and physical phenomena, processes and laws in the process of developing the ecological thinking of students in the horizontal and vertical teaching of natural sciences leads to the development of concepts of ecological thinking in students, to the thoroughness of the knowledge they have received in the field of social sciences, and to their deep assimilation.

Effective implementation of interdisciplinary communication in the course of the lesson, preparation of students to receive new educational materials, implementation of interdisciplinary and intersubjective connections, creation of problem situations, as well as planning and skillful conduct of each lesson requires deep and thorough preparation from the teacher. This, in turn, serves to increase the effectiveness of the lesson.

One of the necessary and priority directions for general education schools is the renewal of the educational content, which creates the need to move the lesson to the basis of modernized, improved and innovative technologies, relying on integrated experiences and ideas. Because the lesson is the main basis of education. The student's knowledge is strengthened during the in-depth study of academic subjects.

In fact, it is possible to understand the interdependent development of various events that occur in nature and society, and the relationships between them, only on the basis of interdisciplinarity. Studying nature and social sciences separately leads to the formation of scattered knowledge about them. Such knowledge does not allow for the formation of a vision of the integrity of nature and society, the role of humanity in nature, the need for a systematic approach to the correct understanding of the essence of the global problems facing humanity and its rational solution. The rapid development of science and technology in foreign countries creates complex problems for scientists. Therefore, instilling new theoretical and practical knowledge about the laws of nature and social development into the content of education

It is extremely necessary to train pedagogues with high knowledge, skills, skills and competences in order for students to acquire the necessary knowledge, skills, skills and competences in the interaction of sciences, social life experiences and knowledge important for various fields of science.

. Today, a new approach to the integration of general education subjects begins. Interdisciplinarity program addresses the problem of convergence and integration of closely related disciplines.

In order to achieve these tasks, it is necessary to select the interdisciplinary content of each subject in order to scientifically substantiate the interdisciplinary connection in the educational process, to form an interconnected system of educational subjects using modern educational technologies used in the educational process.

When students of general education schools observe an object or phenomenon in natural conditions, they perceive them not as a separate object, but as an important part of the whole ecosystem, they perceive them not as a separate object, but as an important part of the whole ecosystem, to understand the interdependence and connection between them. they strive. As a result of this, students can distinguish the unique aspects of the particular object that is brought to their attention, find answers to the questions they are interested in based on their comparison with the objects with the characteristic of interaction, and grouping of their common aspects.

Integrative learning offers movement from simple to complex, from knowing to knowledge, from chaos to harmony, from curiosity to mastery and creativity. Words, the secret of numbers, green characters seek to reveal the secrets of ancient legends. He embarks on a journey through space and time.

As an object of knowledge activity, nature has the opportunity to provide sufficient information to schoolchildren about natural phenomena, their characteristics, interrelationships between them, and the importance of the natural environment in human life.

In particular, in the process of teaching students of general education schools, by connecting literature with social sciences horizontally and vertically, inculcating chemical and physical concepts, forming in them a careful attitude towards the environment, nature, feeling the interrelationship of living and inanimate nature. In addition, it makes them interested in learning the laws of nature and society.

A theoretical analysis of the content of natural sciences taught in general education schools shows that they contain teaching materials that provide information about biological knowledge to one degree or another. Each of them is important in the implementation of certain tasks and encourages students to approach nature and society, to be in constant communication with it. It should be noted that the possibilities of educational subjects in shaping the interest of schoolchildren in learning about nature and society are not the same. In this place, the leading place of natural sciences, the expression of knowledge of ecological thinking based on a certain system sequence in their structural structure, allows students to get reasonable information about the course of nature and society events and processes, to form their interest in learning about nature:

- drawing students' attention to the main aspects of academic subjects, which are of primary importance in revealing the important ideas of science;
- constantly increasing the complexity of perception, expanding the scope of students' creative initiative and independence of educational activities, using various types of didactic tools to effectively establish interdisciplinary communication in the multidisciplinary educational process, gradually increasing organizational work on the use of interdisciplinary communication in the educational process;
- achieving mastery of educational subjects in a mutually organic unity with the help of various didactic tools;
- creating creative cooperation between teachers and students;

Currently, it is considered as a factor that solves integration and pedagogical problems in modern general education schools, activates school activities, increases the potential of the team of pedagogues, and finds optimal ways to influence them.

In fact, in today's educational system, students' knowledge of interdisciplinary communication is implemented through the application of information technologies. This makes it possible to implement large-scale measures to create all the necessary conditions for raising a physically, mentally healthy, mature generation capable of taking responsibility for the future of our country.

The education system has the task of forming and developing the culture of information acquisition and processing of students in the daily life and activities of students. In the successful course of this process, the teacher becomes a consultant, a guide, a manager of the educational process. The teacher assigns the functions of information distribution to information technologies.

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